

Synthesis of Some New Heterocycles from 4'-Amino Flavone

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Manuscript received 5 November 1982, accepted 24 June 1983

A convenient synthesis, with good yields, for 4'-amino flavone (VI) using sodium dithionite as a reducing agent is presented. A few disubstituted thioureas (VIIa, b, c) have been prepared from VI. 4'-Hydrazino-flavone (IX) has been synthesised for the first time and has been used as an intermediate for the synthesis of some 4'-pyrazole and 4'-pyrazoline substituted flavones (XII and XIII).

REPORTS on the chemistry of 4'-amino flavone (VI) are limited. Marcus *et al*¹ prepared 4'-nitro flavone (V) by the direct nitration of flavone and reduced it to VI using Sn and HCl. Doyle *et al*² prepared V from *p*-nitro-benzoyl chloride and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone. Reports of further work are restricted to the preparation of an azo dye and a diacetyl derivative¹ and the preparation of some *bis*-azo derivatives³. Gowan and Wheeler used V and VI in the study of the mechanism of the Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement⁴. Another report⁵ gives some data mainly on the pK_a values of VI.

As part of a research programme aimed at studying various new synthetic chromone heterocycles, we present here a synthesis of VI more convenient than what has been reported so far, and the synthesis of some new heterocyclic derivatives based on VI.

Thus, we have synthesised V (Scheme 1) by directly condensing I and II in presence of pyridine

Scheme 1

and POCl_3 . The ester (III) obtained was converted to its corresponding 1,3-diketone (IV) by a Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement and cyclised to V by heating in an acidic medium. V was reduced to VI using sodium dithionite.

Scheme 2 illustrates the synthesis of some disubstituted thioureas (VIIIa, b, c) by reacting VI with some phenylisothiocyanates (VIIa, b, c).

Scheme 2

- a: Ar = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
- b: Ar = $-\textit{p}\text{-Cl}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$
- c: Ar = $-\textit{p}\text{-OH}_2-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$

4'-Hydrazino flavone (IX) is synthesised (Scheme 3) by diazotisation followed by reduction of VI and has been used as an intermediate in the synthesis of 4'-[3,5-dimethyl-1(H)pyrazole]-flavone (XII) and 4'-[3,5,5-trimethyl-2(H)pyrazoline]-flavone (XIII). The same flavones have also been synthesised in our laboratory via the corresponding pyrazole⁶ and pyrazoline⁷ carboxylic acids and the samples obtained by both the methods show identical tlc, m.p., m.m.p. and spectral data.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries in a paraffin bath and are uncorrected. UV spectra are recorded in methanol; ir spectra (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) in KBr pellets; nmr (chemical shifts in δ ppm) in CDCl_3 .

o-(*p*-Nitrobenzyloxy)acetophenone (III): To a cooled solution of I (0.0065 mole) and II (0.007 mole) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was added POCl_3 with shaking. The mixture was stirred for 3 hr under

Scheme 3

anhydrous conditions, the temperature being maintained at 70-80°. The product (III) was obtained by pouring the reaction mixture onto ice-HCl (excess) and filtering the precipitated compound. The product was washed with an ice cold solution of NaOH (2*N*) to remove any unreacted compounds and recrystallised from methanol to give colourless crystals, m.p. 90-91° (Lit. m.p. 91-92°), yield 91%.

4'-Nitro-2-hydroxydibenzoylmethane (IV) : III (0.01 mole) was dissolved in dry pyridine (25 ml) and crushed, dry KOH (0.02 mole) was added. The mixture was stirred under anhydrous conditions for 3 hr at 45° during which it passed through a series of colour and viscosity changes. The mixture was then poured onto ice-HCl and the yellow precipitate (IV) was filtered, washed with water and dried, m.p. 196-198° (Lit.^a m.p. 198-221°), yield 80%.

4'-Nitro flavone (V) : IV (5 g) was taken in 250 ml ethanol/sulphuric (9 : 1 v/v) and heated strongly under reflux for 4 hr when V separated out. The solution was cooled and the filtered precipitate washed successively with water, cold NaOH (2*N*) and water and dried. V was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give colourless crystals, m.p. 242-244° (Lit.^a m.p. 244-246°), yield 90%.

4'-Amino flavone : V (0.02 mole) was taken in 300 ml ethanol/water (2 : 1 v/v) and heated under reflux. Hydros (sodium dithionite) (0.025 mole) was gradually added into the flask till the compound dissolved completely to give an orange coloured solution. An excess of approximately 1 g was then added and the solution refluxed for further 2 hr. After this, the alcohol was vacuum distilled and the remaining solution poured into 200 ml hot conc. HCl and heated further until all smell of SO₂ disappeared. The solution was filtered hot, cooled and neutralised under cold conditions with NH₄OH to give VI, which was crystallised from xylene to give golden yellow needles, m.p. 233-235° (Lit.^{1,4} m.p. 232-236°), yield 90%. IR : 3350 (Ar-NH₂), 1625 (C=O).

1,3-Disubstituted thioureas (VIII a, b, c) : VIII a, b, c were prepared by heating the appropriate isothiocyanate (VII a, b, c) (0.015 mole) with VI (0.01 mole) in ethanol for 4 hr. The solutions were filtered hot and the compounds VIII crystallised out on cooling. VIII a, m.p. 215-18°. (Found : C, 70.94 ; H, 4.32 ; N, 7.54 ; S, 8.62. C₂₂H₁₆O₃N₂S requires C, 70.94 ; H, 4.33 ; N, 7.52 ; S, 8.61%). VIII b, m.p. 220-23°. VIII c, m.p. 210-13°.

4'-Hydrazino flavone (IX) : VI (1.5 g) in HCl solution (5%, 50 ml), was diazotised at 0-5° by adding NaNO₂ solution (5 ml, 10%), and stirring for 0.5 hr after the addition, at the same temperature. The clear solution was then added slowly to a cold aqueous solution of Na₂SO₃ (5 g in 50 ml) with stirring. The solution was allowed to stand at room temp. for further 2 hr and then neutralised under cold conditions with HCl when a dark red precipitate of 4'-hydrazino flavone hydrochloride separated out. The hydrochloride was used directly for further reactions.

4'-(3,5-Dimethyl-pyrazole) flavone (XII) : IX (0.01 mole) and acetylacetone (X) (0.015 mole) were taken in glacial acetic acid and heated for 1 hr after which conc. HCl (0.1 ml) was added to the solution and the mixture refluxed for further 2 hr. The solution was poured onto ice and the product (XII) which separated out was washed successively with water, dil. HCl, water and dried. Recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 146-47°, yield : 83%. UV : 275, 312 nm. IR : 1630 (>C=O) ; 1120, 1220 (C-O-C) ; 1550, 1600 (γ -pyrone ring) ; 2910, 3030 (=C-CH₃ of pyrazole). NMR : 2.24 (s, 3H, 3-CH₃ of pyrazole), 2.4 (s, 3H, 5-CH₃ of pyrazole), 6.8 (s, 1H, H-4 of pyrazole, 7.0-8.0 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

4'-(3,5,5-Trimethyl-pyrazoline) flavone (XIII) : IX (0.01 mole) and mesityl oxide (XI) (0.015 mole) were taken in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and refluxed for 1 hr after which conc. HCl (0.1 ml) was added and the heating continued for further 3 hr. The solution was poured onto crushed ice with stirring.

when XIII separated out. The precipitate was filtered, washed with dil. HCl, water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 168°, yield 76%. UV: 240, 295-310 nm, 385 nm (pyrazoline). IR: 1640 (>C=O); 1130, 1220 (C-O-C); 1565, 1595 (γ -pyrone ring); 1605 ($-\text{C=N}$ of pyrazole); 1370 (gem-dimethyl of pyrazoline). NMR: 1.6 (s, 6H, gem-dimethyl of pyrazoline), 2.1 (s, 3H, 3-methyl of pyrazoline), 2.85 (s, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of pyrazoline), 6.8 (s, 1H, H-3 of benzopyran), 7.3-8.4 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. V. V. Nadkarny, Director, N.S.R.L. for help and guidance. One of the authors (P.S.F.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for

financial support and the other (L.C.) thanks M/s. Mahindra and Mahindra for a generous fellowship.

References

1. M. T. BOGERT and J. K. MARCUS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 88.
2. B. G. DOYLE, F. GOGAN, J. E. GOWAN, J. KEANE and T. S. WHEELER, *Proc. Royal Dublin Soc.*, 1948, **24**, 291.
3. U. GERES and G. WURM, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1975, **77**, 308.
4. J. E. GOWAN and T. S. WHEELER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1925.
5. A. I. TOLMACHEV, Zh. N. BELAYA and L. M. SHULEZHKO, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1968, **38**, 1139.
6. P. S. FERNANDES and D. H. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 165.
7. P. S. FERNANDES and D. L. M. MENDES, (Communicated).
8. P. N. WADODKAR and M. G. MARATHEY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 145.